

FUNCTIONAL-SEMANTIC FEATURES OF GRADATION IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES.

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Abstract

This article deals with the problems of lexicology and stylistics in linguistics which studies the graduonimic words which are one of the important field of the language. It is filed that the degree of the gradation related with the corresponding factor on the scale, and for that reason categorical precise gradational standards in the language. The common degree or norm of a person a commonly has no extraordinary potential of determination. This function is stated by way of many researchers. It is really worth noting that the indications of the highlighted organizations differ, first of all, in the diploma of graduality of the sign, that is, they occupy extraordinary factors of the scale, growing and reducing in relation to the center factor (norm).

Keywords: gradation, scale, statistic indicators, gradual concepts, precise point, beginning point, ending point, conjunctions

Introduction

As the world becomes increasingly interconnected, the need for bilingual individuals is also on the rise. With globalization, it is important for people to be able to communicate in more than one language. Graduonimic words, or words that are the same in both English and Uzbek languages, are a great way to bridge the gap between these two languages.

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in creating graduonimic words in English and Uzbek languages. These words not only help individuals who are bilingual, but also aid in cross-cultural communication and understanding. By creating more graduonimic words, we are not only promoting bilingualism, but also fostering a greater sense of understanding and connection between different cultures. These words serve as a bridge between languages and help to break down barriers that may exist in communication. Language is a powerful tool that enables us to communicate and express our thoughts and emotions. The creation of new words or the adoption of words from other languages is a common practice in linguistics. One interesting phenomenon that has emerged in recent years is the blending of English and Uzbek words to

create new hybrid words known as graduonimic words. Graduonimic words are a result of the increasing interaction between English and Uzbek speakers, particularly in academic and professional settings. These new words reflect the diverse cultural and linguistic influences that shape our modern world. By combining elements from both languages, graduonimic words allow for more nuanced communication and facilitate cross-cultural understanding.

Research methods

In the manner of learning the topic, the strategies of comparative – go sectional analysis, factor analysis, linguistic modeling, contextual analysis, distributive, statistical and conceptual evaluation are used. It is regarded that there are interpretations of the norm (the center factor of the scale) no longer solely as a degree such as average, normal. Its distinction from the norm as the common measurement of a signal is that, firstly, it is situational (it is hooked up in a precise state of affairs and context and can't be used outdoor of the context), and secondly, it is greater cellular (because it relies upon on the prerequisites of the context, these prerequisites are no longer the identical in one-of-a-kind contexts and, in turn, justify the trade of the norm), thirdly, modality is covered in its content material. This kind of norm is defined otherwise by way of special researchers relying on which components of it are preferred. For example, Ye.A. Potseluevskiy calls it *occasional* [4,385], Arutyunova, N.D. – *situational* [1,341], Chervenкова, I.V. [3,26] and Sheygal, Ye.I. [5,96] interpret it as a *criterion of modality*.

Results and discussion

In our study, we name the described kind of norm modal-contextual (situational) and as a result mix quite a few definitions. Static symptoms of gradualness in relation to the modal-contextual norm are divided into three types. The first kind consists of indications corresponding to the general of the sign: Goho bunday bahs chiqadi. Odamlarning necha foizi dono, ezgu, sahiy? Necha foizi aksincha, nodon, yovuz, manfaatparast? Albatta, buni hech kim hisoblab ko'rmagan. Hisoblab bo'lmaydi ham! Bir tomondan, biz ko'rkam deb bilgan kishida judayam yetarli qusurlar bor. Xunuk atalgan kishida esa ulug'vorlik uchqunlari topiladi (Omon Muxtor, Muhabbat o'limdan kuchli). [3,25]

The lexical gadgets “ancha/much” and “yetarli/enough” and the conjunction “shuningdek/also, shunchalik/so much, shuning uchun/therefore” regularly show up as indications of the described type. In addition to their functional utility, graduonimic words also serve as a reflection of the cultural

exchange and integration taking place in our globalized world. Through the creation of these hybrid words, speakers of English and Uzbek are able to bridge linguistic barriers and forge connections on a deeper level.

However, it is important to note that the use of graduonimic words should be approached with sensitivity and awareness of the cultural contexts in which they are employed. While these words can be a valuable tool for communication, they should not overshadow or replace the traditional languages and expressions of English and Uzbek. Instead, graduonimic words should be seen as a supplement to existing linguistic frameworks, enhancing the richness and diversity of language. It is imperative to pay interest to some factors of the undertaking of static warning signs of gradation associated to the modal-contextual norm in the text. The modal-contextual norm can also in some instances correspond to the norm interpreted as the middle, easy degree of the sign: He stands through the dozen earlier than the Botticellis in Florence, and he sits on all the benches of the Sistine Chapel in Rome. In Italy he drinks a little too an awful lot wine, and in German he drinks an outstanding deal too tons beer. He usually admires the proper issue anything the proper issue is, and one of these days he's going to write a splendid work (W. Somerset Maugham, *Of Human bondage*); Munkillab qolgan ammam bo'lardi. O'ta xudojo'y kampir edi. Bolaligimda oldiga o'tkazib qo'yib, bir gapni ko'paytardi. (O'tkir Hoshimov, *Daftar hoshiyasidagi bitiklar*).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the creation of graduonimic words in English and Uzbek languages is a positive step towards promoting bilingualism and cultural understanding. These words help to strengthen the bond between different languages and allow for more seamless communication between individuals from different backgrounds. It is important to continue to explore and expand on these shared words to further enhance cross-cultural communication and cooperation. So, it is worth noting that this confidence, like the level of a semantic sign, tends to the limit: the subject of speech is almost sure that what is reported is true (in this case at the borderline level of the sign), and his doubts are insignificant. Pragmatic conditions for the manifestation of predictability indicators in speech (text) can be used in the following situations. First, these are situations in which the main focus is not on the level of the sign, but on its presence (even if it is little), that is, the exact norm (level) of the sign will not be of great importance. Such situations were considered in the examples given above with more or less indicators

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